

DEVELOPMENT AND QUALITY CONTROL OF HYDROGEL FACIAL MASK WITH BIOACTIVES OF *ALOE VERA* AND *CAMELLIA SINENSIS L.*

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ABSTRACT

Facial masks have evolved from traditional methods to modern formulations, incorporating natural ingredients and technologies such as hydrogels, which promote hydration, regeneration, and skin protection. Ingredients like *Camellia sinensis L.* and *Aloe vera* stand out for their antioxidant and moisturizing properties, reflecting the growing demand for effective and safe cosmetics. This trend strengthens pharmaceutical innovation and emphasizes skin health by combining aesthetics and functionality. This experimental and laboratory-based study evaluated the development of a hydrogel facial mask containing bioactive compounds from *Aloe vera* and *Camellia sinensis L.*, aiming to assess the formulation's efficacy and stability. The mask was prepared using sodium alginate and xanthan gum as the main raw materials. Physicochemical quality control tests, including pH, mass, and shrinkage, were conducted on two groups of masks: one stored under controlled conditions and another exposed to high temperatures. Additionally, the swelling index was analyzed. The

collected data indicated that controlled storage better preserved the mask's physical and organoleptic characteristics, whereas heat exposure led to moisture loss and structural

changes. The formulation maintained a stable pH, suitable for facial use, and the high swelling index favored the controlled release of bioactive compounds. The hydrogel mask demonstrated stability and potential for cosmetic application. Further clinical studies and additional testing are recommended to confirm the benefits of the bioactives on the skin. This research reinforces the use of hydrogels with natural bioactives as an effective and safe alternative for topical treatments, offering benefits that meet the demands of the modern cosmetic market.

KEYWORDS: *Aloe vera*. *Camellia sinensis* L.. Hydrogels. Cosmetology. Quality Control. Dermocosmetics.

INTRODUCTION

Facial masks, widely used since antiquity, have evolved from traditional methods to increasingly sophisticated formulations, incorporating natural ingredients while meeting strict safety and efficacy standards. From the earliest masks in ancient Greece and Rome, through Elizabethan England, to the development of kaolin- and clay-based formulations in the 19th century, the use of facial masks has reflected the desire to care for and maintain healthy skin.^{[1][2]} With the growth of industrial cosmetic production in the 20th century, regulatory agencies emerged to ensure product compliance, guaranteeing consumer safety and quality.^[1] At the same time, the interest in natural ingredients, such as plant extracts, has gained strength in modern cosmetics, responding to the demand for products that promote both aesthetics and skin health, protecting against external aggressions.^[3] In Brazil, legislation establishes strict standards for the manufacture of cosmetics, reinforcing the importance of the pharmacist specialized in product formulation and ensuring compliance with good practices.^{[4][5]} This trend highlights the value of skin health and functionality in addition to aesthetic benefits, promoting a safe and effective approach to beauty for consumers. Constant exposure to factors such as ultraviolet radiation and pollution can damage the skin barrier, accelerating aging and causing dermatological problems. In this context, the development of facial masks with natural ingredients that possess antioxidant, moisturizing, and regenerative properties is of great scientific, social, and economic importance, as it promotes quality of life and strengthens the pharmaceutical profession in cosmetic innovation.^{[6][7]}

Camellia sinensis L. and *Aloe vera* are examples of widely valued natural raw materials due to their benefits. *Camellia* is rich in bioactive compounds such as polyphenols and vitamins, which have antimicrobial and antioxidant activity, making it a promising ingredient for

cosmetics with both aesthetic and therapeutic effects.^{[8][9]} *Aloe vera* gel is recognized for its regenerative and moisturizing properties, as well as its ability to form a protective barrier on the skin, favoring healing and protection.^[10] These ingredients complement the advancement of natural components in facial masks and other cosmetics, meeting the demand for products that combine aesthetic benefits with skin health, supported by safety and efficacy. Hydrogels are three-dimensional polymers capable of absorbing large amounts of water and are widely used in cosmetics due to their ability to retain moisture and release active compounds in a controlled manner, making them suitable for moisturizers and skin and hair care.^[11] Based on natural proteins and polysaccharides (such as alginate) or synthetic materials, they present high hydrophilicity, stability, and biodegradability, which make them appropriate for controlled release of ingredients.^{[12][13][14]}

The integration of hydrogels with natural components thus strengthens facial mask formulations. The incorporation of natural raw materials into modern formulations such as hydrogels represents a promising approach to developing cosmetic products that meet the demands of increasingly discerning consumers for quality and safety.^{[15][16]} The present study aimed to develop and evaluate a cosmetic hydrogel formulation enriched with *Camellia sinensis L.* and *Aloe vera* extracts, seeking to explore the synergy between natural raw materials and hydrogel technology, as well as to provide relevant data to support future formulations and practices in cosmetic science.

1. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study is characterized as an experimental laboratory research, conducted at the Pharmaceutics Laboratory of the Universidade Católica Dom Bosco (Laboratory A102). Over the course of one year of research, a hydrogel facial mask containing bioactive compounds from *Aloe vera* and *Camellia sinensis L.* was developed and subjected to a series of physical and chemical quality control tests.

1.1 Materials

The raw materials used in the formulation were obtained from a compounding pharmacy and specialized companies, selected based on strict quality criteria. These companies and pharmacies were chosen considering parameters such as positive reviews, proven reliability, and affiliation or partnerships with the university, ensuring that the materials complied with best pharmaceutical practices to guarantee the safety and efficacy of the formulation.

1.2 Hydrogel Mask Preparation

The preparation process begins with the dispersion of sodium alginate in warm distilled water, followed by homogenization for 20 minutes. In a separate container, xanthan gum was previously mixed with glycerin using indirect heating at 50°C and then incorporated into the alginate gel with circular movements, forming the hydrogel base. Sodium metabisulfite was dissolved in 20 mL of distilled water, and the *Aloe vera* and *Camellia sinensis L.* extracts were added. This solution was then poured into the hydrogel base and homogenized. In parallel, the preservatives methylparaben and propylparaben were dissolved in propylene glycol and incorporated into the base; the fragrance was added at the final stage of preparation, where it was adjusted and evenly distributed. The resulting product was a slightly yellowish gel. The gel was poured into a mold and immersed in a 2% calcium chloride solution for 30 minutes. The composition and concentrations used in the hydrogel mask formulation and the 2% calcium chloride solution are detailed in Table 1.

Table 1: Composition and mass for the preparation of hydrogel mask and 2% calcium chloride solution.

COMPOSITION	MASS (G)	FUNCTION
Hydrogel mask:		
<i>Camellia sinensis L.</i> extract	10.00	Active
<i>Aloe vera</i> extract	6.00	Active
Sodium alginate	2.00	Gelling agent
Xanthan gum	0.50	Thickener, stabilizer
Propylene glycol	2.50	Humectant
Glycerin	10.00	Humectant
Sodium metabisulfite	0.02	Antioxidant, preservative
Methylparaben	0.02	Antimicrobial preservative
Propylparaben	0.10	Antimicrobial preservative
Distilled water	200.00	Solvent
Essence	q.s.	Fragrance
2% Calcium Chloride Solution:		
Calcium chloride	60.00	Thickener
Distilled water	3000.00	Solvent

Source: Author, 2024.

Figure 1: Hydrogel mask submerged in 2% calcium chloride solution.

Quality Control of the Hydrogel Mask

The hydrogel masks were subjected to stability tests addressing physical aspects such as size, color, odor, average weight, and shrinkage, as well as chemical aspects such as pH. Evaluations were performed once, in triplicate, for two distinct groups of masks, using the same analytical methods. The first group was stored under a thin protective plastic film, exposed to environmental conditions and high temperatures ranging from 37°C to 40°C over the course of one week. The second group was packed in sealed individual containers, maintained under controlled temperatures of 25°C to 35°C during the same period. This approach allowed for the observation and comparison of the effects of different storage conditions and temperatures on the integrity and characteristics of the hydrogel masks. In addition, a swelling test was performed on the hydrogel developed.

1.3 Weight Evaluation

For the evaluation of the physical characteristics of the masks, mass measurements were performed using an analytical balance, model Sartorius BP3105. Initially, three mask units were weighed in order to determine the average mass. The mean values obtained were used for subsequent analysis. The samples were weighed on the day of formulation and again after one week, with the purpose of calculating the difference between the two evaluation periods.

1.4 pH Evaluation

To determine the acidity of the samples, three mask units were individually immersed in three glass beakers, each containing 10 mL of distilled water (pH 6.5 ± 0.1), for a period of 2 hours at room temperature. After the immersion period, the pH of the resulting solutions was measured using a pH meter, model PHS3BW BEL. Measurements were performed in triplicate, and the mean values obtained were used for result analysis.

1.5 Shrinkage Evaluation

Accordingly, to evaluate the shrinkage of the hydrogel masks, three samples were measured in triplicate using two parameters: the distance from one cheek to the other (width) and from the forehead to the chin (height). Measurements were taken on the first day after sample formulation. Subsequently, the masks were stored for one week and then measured again. The values obtained at both stages were used for the comparative analysis of shrinkage.

1.6 Swelling Index

The swelling index was subsequently evaluated as described in the Brazilian Pharmacopoeia, 6th edition.^[17] For controlled-release applications, hydrogels are suitable due to their characteristics of biodegradability, biocompatibility, hydrophilicity, chemical stability, and their capacity for solute sorption and desorption^[14]. The swelling index is essential, as it allows for a quantitative assessment of the hydrogel's ability to absorb liquids, directly influencing its efficiency in the controlled release of drugs and its functionality in therapeutic systems.

The initial weight of three mask units was recorded, and each was individually immersed in three glass beakers. Weight measurements were taken using an analytical balance, model Sartorius BP3105, at intervals of 12, 24, 36, 48, 60, and 72 hours throughout the week. The swelling index of the hydrogel masks was then calculated from the measured values by applying the corresponding formula. The graph was subsequently plotted using the average values of the masks, with an uncertainty of 5%.

- W_n = weight of the hydrogel mask after hydration;
- W_o = weight of the hydrogel mask before hydration;
- Swelling Index = $\frac{W_n - W_o}{W_o} \times 100\%$;

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The tests demonstrated that the hydrogel facial masks containing *Aloe vera* and *Camellia sinensis L.* bioactives presented good initial quality, with adequate physical and chemical properties, including uniform dimensions, consistent weight, and pleasant texture. However, storage conditions had a significant influence on these characteristics, resulting in alterations that varied according to the type of packaging and temperature over time. The measurement uncertainty used for the weight, height, and width graphs of the three masks, defined as the interval that expresses the reliability of the measurements by considering the inherent variations of the measurement process, was determined using the standard deviation of the means for each data set. This calculation reflects the dispersion of individual values in relation to the mean, providing a quantitative estimate of the precision of the measurements performed.

Figure 2: Hydrogel mask ready inside protective packaging.

The hydrogel masks exhibited satisfactory organoleptic characteristics immediately after production, with an elastic texture, absence of ruptures, a refreshing sensation, and a well-perceptible fragrance of the chosen essence. Visually, they appeared transparent and thin, providing user comfort. After one week, the masks kept under constant light and protected only with plastic film preserved their pleasant odor and desired transparency; however, exposure to high temperatures resulted in significant moisture loss, making them thinner and drier, which compromised their original texture. In contrast, the masks stored in sealed packaging and kept at milder temperatures preserved their organoleptic and physical

characteristics after one week, maintaining satisfactory levels of moisture, thickness, fragrance, elasticity, and structural integrity, thus ensuring comfort and preservation of texture.

2.1 Weight Evaluation

The results regarding the mass of the hydrogel masks exposed to heat indicate a significant weight loss over time. Initially, the average weight of these masks was 6.48g, which drastically decreased to 0.60g after one week, as shown in Graph 1, suggesting substantial water loss due to evaporation. The samples were stored only with plastic film and exposed to light and heat, conditions that explain this pronounced mass reduction. In contrast, the masks stored in sealed packaging showed a weight reduction within the expected range for a one-week period, decreasing from an initial average of 13g to 10g, as shown in Graph 2. These results highlight the importance of storing hydrogel masks in hermetic packaging that preserves moisture and controls temperature,^[20] which are essential to maintaining physical integrity, application efficacy, and the stability of bioactive properties throughout the storage period.^[21]

Graph 1: Average weight of masks exposed to high temperatures, initial weight and weight after one week.

Graph 2: Average weight of masks exposed to lower temperatures, initial weight and weight after one week.

2.2 pH Evaluation

In the study, the average pH of the hydrogel masks stored under high temperature and low protection conditions was 5.83 immediately after production, a slightly acidic value probably related to the residual presence of the 2% calcium chloride solution. After one week, the pH of these samples stabilized at 6, demonstrating that the formulation has good buffering capacity, correcting initial variations.^[18] In comparison, the masks stored in sealed packaging and at lower temperatures maintained a constant pH of 6 both at the beginning and after one week, indicating that the pH of the formulation remains stable and reliable regardless of storage and temperature conditions.^[18] The ideal pH for facial cosmetics is between 4.5 and 6.5, which is compatible with the natural pH of the skin and is essential to preserve its protective barrier and minimize the risk of irritation.^[19] These results confirm the stability of the mask's pH over time, ensuring both the efficacy of the bioactives and safety for application on sensitive skin.

2.3 Shrinkage Evaluation

The results regarding the width and height measurements of the hydrogel masks exposed to high temperatures indicate significant shrinkage after one week of storage, as shown in Graph 3 (A and B). The initial average width of these masks was 13.8cm, which decreased to 13.4cm after one week, while the height decreased from 11.8cm to 11.3cm during the same period. This shrinkage can be attributed to water evaporation, since the masks were stored only wrapped in plastic film and exposed to light and heat, conditions that favored moisture loss and the consequent reduction in dimensions. In contrast, the masks stored in sealed packaging and kept at mild temperatures showed minimal reduction in height and width

dimensions between the time of manufacture and one week later, as observed in Graph 4 (A and B).

These results highlight the importance of proper storage conditions, such as the use of hermetic packaging and controlled temperatures, to preserve the physical integrity of hydrogel masks, maintaining their properties and effectiveness over time.^[20]

Graph 3: Average height (A) and width (B) of masks exposed to high temperatures after formation and after one week.

Graph 4: Average height (A) and width (B) of masks exposed to lower temperatures after formation and after one week.

2.4 Swelling Index

Hydrogels, the basis of the formulation, are three-dimensionally crosslinked hydrophilic polymers with a high capacity to absorb water molecules.^[12] Therefore, analyzing swelling values through graphs is necessary for the quality control of the masks.^[13] In this formulation,

sodium alginate was chosen, as it provides the hydrogel with hydrophilic characteristics and a high water absorption capacity. Sodium alginate has properties that facilitate the rapid formation of hydrogels, especially in the presence of bivalent or trivalent ions (Ca^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Al^{3+}), which promote crosslinking due to interactions between alginate and the ions, resulting in improvements in mechanical strength, cohesion, and rigidity.^[22] As illustrated in Graph 5, the swelling index of the hydrogel masks increased rapidly within the first 12 hours, followed by a gradual growth until stabilizing after approximately 36 hours. This initial rapid increase in the swelling index indicates a high water absorption capacity, favored by the formation of hydrogen bonds that promote the expansion of the hydrogel's polymeric structure. The stabilization of the index in the subsequent hours suggests that the hydrogel reached its maximum water retention capacity.

Graph 5: Average swelling index of hydrogel masks in distilled water.

The uncertainty presented in the graph is 5%. The high swelling index is a desirable characteristic for hydrogels in cosmetic applications, as it indicates an excellent capacity for water absorption and retention. This property is essential for the controlled release of active ingredients onto the skin, allowing the formulation to deliver them effectively and over a prolonged period, which is beneficial for continuous skin hydration and treatment.

3. CONCLUSIONS

The results obtained during the quality tests of the hydrogel facial mask with *Aloe vera* and *Camellia sinensis L.* bioactives provided relevant data on the stability and effectiveness of the product. In summary, the study showed that the hydrogel masks exhibited adequate organoleptic and physicochemical characteristics immediately after production. The masks kept under controlled storage conditions, with sealed packaging and mild temperatures,

preserved their moisture, texture, and pH properties over the course of one week, demonstrating stability and safety for skin application. On the other hand, storage in environments with high temperatures and low protection resulted in significant changes in the structure and moisture of the masks, negatively affecting the texture and thickness of the product.

The stability of the pH, which remained within the ideal range for facial products, and the high swelling index confirm the efficacy and safety of the hydrogel formulated with sodium alginate, highlighting its high water retention capacity and potential for the controlled release of bioactives. The development of hydrogel masks containing *Aloe vera* and *Camellia sinensis L.* bioactives proved to be promising for the cosmetic sector, combining efficacy in moisture retention, chemical stability, and sensory comfort. The analyses carried out confirmed that storage conditions directly influence the physical and organoleptic properties of the product, with storage in hermetic packaging and under mild temperature being essential to preserve its original characteristics. Thus, the study reinforces the feasibility of using hydrogels with natural extracts as an effective and safe alternative for topical treatments, offering aesthetic and functional benefits that meet the demands of the modern cosmetic market.

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